

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 70

Rev. Dr. Michael Harvey Koplitz

The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 70

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 70:0 For the choir director. <i>A Psalm</i> of David; for a memorial.</p>	<p>Psa. 70:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ לְדָוִד</p>
<p>Psa. 70:1 "O God, <i>hasten</i> to deliver me; O LORD, hasten to my help! ² "Let those be ashamed and humiliated Who seek my ¹life; Let those be turned back and dishonored Who delight ²in my hurt. ³ "Let those be ¹turned back because of their shame Who say, "Aha, aha!"</p>	<p>לְהִזְכִּיר : ² אֱלֹהִים לְהִצִּילֵנִי יְהוָה לְעֲזָרְתִּי חַוָּשָׁה : ³ יִבְשׁוּ וַיִּחְפְּרוּ מִבְּקִשְׁי נַפְשִׁי יִסְגּוּ אֲחֹזֵר וַיִּכְלְמוּ חֲפִצֵי רַעְתִּי : ⁴ יָשׁוּבוּ עַל-עֵקֶב בְּשִׁתְּם הָאֹמְרִים הֵאֱחָת אֶהְיֶה : ⁵ וְשִׁישׁוּ וַיִּשְׁמְחוּ אִבְיָךְ כָּל- מְבַקְשֵׁיךָ וַיֹּאמְרוּ תִמְדֵּד יִגְדֵּל אֱלֹהִים אֶהְיֶה יִשׁוּעָתְךָ : ⁶ וַאֲנִי אֶעֱנֶה וַאֲבִיוֹן אֱלֹהִים חַוָּשָׁה-לִּי עֲזָרִי וּמִפְּלִטֵי אֲתָהּ יְהוָה אֶל-תְּאַחֵר :</p>
<p>Psa. 70:4 Let all who seek You rejoice and be glad in You; And let those who love Your salvation say continually, "Let God be magnified." ⁵ But "I am afflicted and needy; ^bHasten to me, O God! You are my help and my deliverer; O LORD, do not delay.</p>	<p>יִגְדֵּל אֱלֹהִים אֶהְיֶה יִשׁוּעָתְךָ : ⁶ וַאֲנִי אֶעֱנֶה וַאֲבִיוֹן אֱלֹהִים חַוָּשָׁה-לִּי עֲזָרִי וּמִפְּלִטֵי אֲתָהּ יְהוָה אֶל-תְּאַחֵר :</p>

References

Psalm 70:1

^aPs 40:13-17; 70:1-5

Psalm 70:2

¹Or *soul*

²Or *to injure me*

^aPs 35:4, 26

Psalm 70:3

¹Some mss read *appalled*

^aPs 40:15

Psalm 70:5

^aPs 40:17

^bPs 141:1

Targum

Psa. 70:1 For praise; composed by David, for remembrance; concerning the handful of incense. ² O God, [hasten] to deliver us, O LORD, hasten to our aid. ³ Let those who seek my soul be ashamed and disgraced; let those who desire my ruin draw back and be dishonored. ⁴ Let them turn back, because they lay in wait for me; let those who say about me "We have rejoiced, rejoiced!" be punished as befits their shame. ⁵ Let those who seek instruction from you be glad and exult in your word, and let those who love your redemption always say, "May the glory of the LORD be magnified." ⁶ But I am poor and lowly, O God; hasten to me, you are my help and salvation; O LORD, do not delay.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

In this Psalm, David pleaded for his return to power. The following parable fits the situation.

A king became vexed at the shepherd. He chased away the flock, tore down the animal shed, and dismissed the shepherd. After a time, the king gathered the sheep and rebuilt the shed. The king did not restore the shepherd to his position. The shepherd lamented, "Behold the sheep are gathered in, the shed is rebuilt, but I am not remembered.

Superscript

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory. By David, to serve as a memorial.

Verse one

David makes a twofold appeal to the LORD. The first appeal is for a judgment that would frustrate the criminal intentions of his foes. The second is to deliver him from their hands.

O God, make hast to deliver me, to help me, O God.

Verse two

Only by failing can ordinary people become aware that they have been evil in the past and are still morally unworthy.

So that they may be deceived and unmasked, those that seek my soul; that they may fall back and be ashamed, those who desire my hurt.

Verse three

Only by humiliation can evil people be made to return to the LORD.

Let them turn back by reason of their shame, those who would call out even now: O brother, brother!

Verse four

David believed that if the LORD delivered him back into power that his enemies would realize the evil that they were doing.

But let all those that seek You blossom forth blissfully and rejoice in You, and let such as love your salvation say at all times: God reveals his greatness.

Verse five

But I a poor and defenseless, O God, make haste unto me. You are my help and my deliverer; O God, do not tarry.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory. By David, to serve as a memorial.

O God, make hast to deliver me, to help me, O God.

So that they may be deceived and unmasked, those that seek my soul; that they may fall back and be ashamed, those who desire my hurt.

Let them turn back by reason of their shame, those who would call out even now: O brother, brother!

But let all those that seek You blossom forth blissfully and rejoice in You, and let such as love your salvation say at all times: God reveals his greatness.

But I a poor and defenseless, O God, make haste unto me. You are my help and my deliverer; O God, do not tarry.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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